

Notes

Chalcones. XII. Potential Germicides derived from 1-Hydroxy-2-Acetonaphthone

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A large number of chalcones have been studied^{1-5,7,10-17} against various bacterial infections probably due to the presence of α, β -unsaturated carbonyl ($-\text{CO}-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$) group, which may react with bacterial protoplasm. Geiger and Conn during the course of chemical studies⁶ on α, β -unsaturated ketones observed that antibacterial activity seemed to be due to the presence of above mentioned group. Misra *et al.* have reported^{8,9,11,13,21} the germicidal activity of a number of naphthyl and phenanthryl chalcones. Further, Wilson and Floyed⁹ have also reported that by the use of hydroxy chalcones the adrenaline was protected from destruction. These observations have prompted the author to synthesize hydroxy naphthyl chalcone analogues as potential germicides.

In the present communication the preparation of hydroxy naphthyl chalcone analogues have been described with a view to see their growth inhibiting effect on *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. These compounds were obtained by the condensation of 1-hydroxy-2-acetonaphthone with different aryl aldehydes in presence of saturated alcoholic caustic potash solution. 1-Hydroxy-2-acetonaphthone reacted smoothly with different aryl aldehydes within 24-48 hr and the yields were good in general with a few exception. 1-Hydroxy-2-acetonaphthyl-(3 or 4) hydroxy styryl ketones (compound nos. 1, 2) and 1-hydroxy-2-naphthyl-(2 or 4) hydroxy-3-methoxy styryl ketones (compound nos. 9 and 10) were obtained in 30-40% yield of the theoretical value. Moreover, condensation of these compounds in presence of concentrated alkali solution resulted in dark coloured resinified products which could not be crystallised.

It is important to note that during the condensation of hydroxy benzaldehydes with methyl aryl ketones in presence of concentrated alkali solution dark coloured tarry masses of unknown composition are obtained and 10% potassium hydroxide solution at low temperature gave crystalline compounds, comparatively in good yield. On the other hand hydroxy methyl aryl ketones did not produce such products. This may be due to the resinification of benzaldehydes and other side reactions.

The compounds were characterised by their elemental analyses and halochromism with conc. sulfuric acid (produced different transient colours). The presence of α, β -unsaturated carbonyl group in the synthesized compounds was confirmed by recording infrared absorption spectra of a few compounds. There was a strong absorption band in the range of 1667-1685 cm^{-1} which is a characteristic of the said functional group¹⁸.

Germicidal Activity

Germicidal activity was determined by Agar-cup method. The reaction mixture consists of compound 100-150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of 50% aqueous-ethanol. The inocula were prepared from stationary culture and inhibition of growth was checked at an incubation temperature of $32^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ after 24 hr. The strength is reported by measuring the diameter of zone of inhibition in mm and the results were standardized against benzoic acid (Table 1).

Experimental

The naphthyl chalcone analogues were synthesized by adopting the method reported earlier⁷⁻⁸ and purified by repeated crystallisations from ethanol unless otherwise mentioned. The homogeneity was tested by thin-layer chromatography on silica gel-G using ethylacetate petroleum ether ($40^\circ-60^\circ$) as reported earlier¹⁹ and the spots were located by virtue of their own colour, one typical example is cited below.

Equimolar quantities of 1-hydroxy-2-acetonaphthone and 2-chlorobenzaldehyde were dissolved in aldehyde free ethanol, and the condensation was effected in presence of 30% alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution at room temperature. After 24 hr crystals of 1-hydroxy-2-naphthyl-2-chloro-styryl ketone were deposited. On recrystallisation from ethanol orange coloured crystals were obtained (Table 1).

All melting points are uncorrected. The compounds were analysed for C-H combustion and the results were within $\pm 0.5\%$ of the theoretical value.

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TABLE I—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND BIOCHEMICAL SCREENING DATA OF HYDROXY NAPHTHYL CHALCONES

R	Colour and Crystal shape	Yield %	M.P. °C	Time of reaction in hrs.	$\nu_{max.}$ C=O	Halochromism Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Dia. of zone of inhib. in mm.
3-HO	Yellow globules	30	111	48	1669	red	—
4-OH ^A	Yellow clusters	32	127	48	—	blood red	—
2-Cl	Orange needles	85	140	25	1680	brown	12
3-Cl	Orange red plates	82	131	28	1675	violet	11
4-Cl	Orange needles	87	183	26	1685	red	12
2-OMe ^B	Orange globules	70	152	32	—	pink	10
3-OMe	Orange plates	65	147	32	1667	red	9
4-OMe ^A	Red plates	68	156	38	—	cherry-red	8
2-OH-3-OMe	Orange needles	45	127	40	—	dark-red	—
4-OH-3-OMe ^B	Yellow prisms	41	106	47	—	violet	—
5-Br-4-OH-3-OMe	Yellow needles	63	137	33	1683	brown	8
2,3-(OMe) ₂	Orange plates	58	92	28	—	red	8
3-4(OMe) ₂	Yellow globules	61	113	88	1678	red	7
2-Me ^B	Orange needles	52	126	34	—	brown	8
3-Me	Red plates	47	105	30	1677	brown	7
4-Me	Orange prisms	50	138	33	1671	violet	8
Benzoic acid							12

Crystallised from—A = ethylacetate; B = benzene.

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